

1 **Chasing bubbles: towards a standardized approach for quantifying methane**
2 **ebullition using bubble traps in streams and rivers**

3

4 *Adam Bednarik^{1*}, Eva Darenova¹, Helena Cvetkovic², Charlotte Doebke^{2,3}, Clemens*
5 *Karwautz², Lukas Kokrda¹, Natalia Kowalska¹, & Katrin Attermeyer^{2,3}*

6 *¹ Department of Matters and Energy Fluxes, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech*
7 *Academy of Sciences, Belidla 4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic*

8 *² Department of Functional and Evolutionary Ecology, University of Vienna, Djerassiplatz 1,*
9 *1030 Vienna, Austria*

10 *³ WasserCluster Lunz- Biologische Station, Dr. Carl Kupelwieser Promenade 5, 3293 Lunz am*
11 *See, Austria*

12

13 *Corresponding author: Adam Bednarik (bednarik.a@czechglobe.cz)

14

15 **Abstract**

16 Ebullition transports large quantities of the potent greenhouse gas methane (CH₄) from stream sediments
17 into the atmosphere. However, the use of different sampling designs complicates comparisons of CH₄
18 emissions estimates between studies. Here, we present the first systematic review of sampling designs
19 used in the past for assessing fluvial CH₄ ebullition rates. In addition, we conducted field experiments to
20 estimate the optimal number of bubble traps and the length of the sampling period, and to assess
21 uncertainties in determining CH₄ content in the emitted bubbles. Our results demonstrate considerable
22 spatial variability in bubble fluxes and CH₄ content in the bubbles (0.01–67%), necessitating a larger
23 number of bubble traps than typically deployed in streams. Using fewer traps leads to greater deviations
24 in CH₄ ebullition estimates than shorter deployment times. Therefore, the robust sampling design should
25 account for strong small-scale heterogeneity in streams through an adequate number of bubble traps and
26 link bubble fluxes to trap-specific gas content. It should also consider the risk of CH₄ concentration
27 decreases in accumulated bubbles over a few days, primarily due to redissolution, followed by oxidation
28 and leakage.

29 **Keywords:** greenhouse gas; methane emissions; bubble trap; chamber, stable carbon isotopes

30 **Synopsis**

31 Methane ebullition estimates are challenged by the different sampling designs. Based on a systematic
32 review and field experiments, we present recommendations for a standardized approach to assessing
33 methane ebullition.

34

35 **Data availability statement**

36 Data and metadata are available in the Zenodo data repository at
37 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18743758> (Bednarik et al. 2026).

38 ***Introduction***

39 Streams and rivers have been recognized to emit methane (CH₄) to a similar extent as lakes or reservoirs,
40 but a limited number of CH₄ ebullition measurements still hampers more robust estimates of CH₄ fluxes
41 from running waters^{1,2}. The CH₄ flux assessments from streams and rivers are dominated by
42 measurements of diffusive fluxes, with ebullition measurements accounting for only 8% of the records³.
43 These studies report a high spatio-temporal variability of ebullition in streams, given by a wide range of
44 both bubble fluxes and bubble CH₄ contents^{4,5}. Thus, there is a critical need for a robust and standardized
45 sampling design for stream ebullition assessments.

46 There are three main approaches for measuring the CH₄ ebullition – floating chambers, bubble traps, and
47 hydroacoustic surveys. When the chambers are connected to a portable analyzer or equipped with a CH₄
48 sensor^{6,7}, ebullition is estimated based on abrupt increases in the CH₄ concentration in the chamber.
49 Alternatively, the calculated diffusive fluxes using Fick's law are subtracted from the total fluxes
50 (diffusive + ebullitive) measured by the chambers in the case of manual gas sampling⁸. Chamber
51 measurements do not provide information on bubble volume and associated CH₄ content and are typically
52 conducted over minutes to hours. In the case of bubble traps often using an inverted funnel design, the
53 combination of the volume of the captured bubbles and their CH₄ content is used to estimate CH₄
54 emission through ebullition. Bubble volumes and subsequent gas analyses are performed manually, or
55 automatically if traps are equipped with pressure and gas sensors, allowing determination of the volume
56 and CH₄ content of accumulated bubbles^{9,10}. Automated bubble traps can provide highly detailed time
57 series of bubble fluxes, enabling temporal variability and its drivers to be identified^{11,12}. However, the
58 automated bubble traps are mainly used in reservoirs because their use may be limited in shallow streams
59 due to their larger size. The number of traps deployed varies in different studies as well as the
60 measurement periods, which range from hours to months^{5,13}. In addition, bubble traps vary in design,
61 material used and size, as well as in their distribution across the site. There is also no consensus on the
62 sampling design or uncertainties related to the chosen sampling strategy. The only existing estimate of the

63 optimum number of traps and sampling period for streams was made by Robison et al. ¹⁴, who
64 recommended deploying 10 traps over 60 days to cover the spatio-temporal variability of CH₄ ebullition.
65 A similar estimate of the optimal number of traps (11) deployed over 39 days was proposed using depth-
66 stratified sampling also for lakes ¹⁵. A partial comparison of the use of floating chambers and bubble traps
67 for estimating ebullition in rivers shows that both methods can produce consistent results ¹⁶. However,
68 ebullition may be underestimated if floating chambers are deployed for only tens of minutes ¹⁷. Finally,
69 hydroacoustic surveys use echo sounders to detect rising bubbles and determine their volume and density
70 over large areas in a short time ^{18,19}. This method is widely applied to quantify CH₄ ebullition in reservoirs
71 and lakes but is limited in rivers, where it is primarily used upstream of dams due to depth-related
72 limitations ²⁰. To date, no systematic overview on the designs used to assess fluvial CH₄ ebullition has
73 been reported.

74 Open questions remain, particularly regarding the correct use of bubble traps. To accurately determine
75 ebullitive fluxes using bubble traps, the volumes of gas collected in bubble traps must be coupled with a
76 specific CH₄ content to estimate the ebullition. Basically, there are two ways to sample the gas for
77 analysis of its content - either by sampling the accumulated gas from the traps ¹⁷, or by collecting fresh
78 bubbles after disturbance of the sediments near the traps ²¹. Studies from various ecosystems suggest that
79 concentration of trapped CH₄ may decline rapidly, potentially due to oxidation or dissolution ^{9,22}. This
80 complicates accurate estimation of CH₄ concentrations in the released bubbles. Similarly, sampling of
81 sediment-disturbed bubbles raises concerns about their comparability to naturally released bubbles, which
82 has rarely been assessed. Thus, although Wik et al. ¹⁵ and Robison et al. ¹⁴ evaluated the number of traps
83 and the deployment time in lakes and streams, respectively, further questions remain regarding the data
84 supporting the best gas sampling practices used to determine CH₄ content for CH₄ ebullition estimates.
85 Consequently, the comparability of ebullition estimates between studies is challenged by the different
86 sampling designs used.

87 The aims of this study were (1) to present a systematic review of the sampling designs used in the past for
88 assessing fluvial CH₄ ebullition rates and (2) to provide a recommendation for a robust sampling design
89 for bubble trap assessments in streams based on experimental measurements. Specifically, we assessed
90 the optimal number of bubble traps and the length of the sampling period in streams, including the
91 optimal method of gas sampling for determination of CH₄ content. We increased the number of bubble
92 traps and shortened the sampling period compared to previous studies to limit the effect of temperature
93 changes on the temporal variability of CH₄ ebullition. Additionally, we focused on a detailed observation
94 of CH₄ concentration changes in trapped bubbles over time.

95 **Methods**

96 ***Systematic review of the sampling designs***

97 Relevant studies were identified through searches in the Web of Science and Scopus databases as well as
98 from published datasets on fluvial CH₄ fluxes³. The assessment of methodology and reporting was
99 conducted based on predefined inclusion and exclusion following standardized criteria according to
100 “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses” (PRISMA) method²³. Briefly,
101 we searched English-language literature for studies reporting field measurements of CH₄ emissions,
102 including ebullition, in various types of running waters. A comprehensive search of Web of Science and
103 Scopus on 29 November 2024 identified 3,659 studies, from which 42 unique studies were included in the
104 final dataset based on the selection criteria (Fig. 1). Details of the search strategy, including keywords,
105 inclusion criteria, and results, are described in the Supplementary Material: Details of systematic review
106 of the sampling designs.

107

108 ***Assessment of robust sampling design for stream ebullitive fluxes***

109 To generate recommendations for bubble rate measurements, we tested the optimal number of bubble
110 traps and the length of the sampling period in Jihlava and Hana streams in Czechia, and in Schweinsbach
111 stream in Austria (1). To generate recommendations for bubble CH₄ content measurements, we monitored
112 the concentration of CH₄ and $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ in trapped bubbles over time in the streams Hana and Kyjovka in
113 Czechia (2.1) and performed additional experiments and calculations to explain the observed changes. We
114 tested for syringe leakage to determine whether the material and connections were permeable to CH₄
115 (2.2), and assessed the potential effects of CH₄ oxidation (2.3) and bubble redissolution (2.4). Finally, we
116 compared the CH₄ concentration and $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ in bubbles naturally and artificially released from stream
117 sediments in Kyjovka (3). Characteristics of the investigated streams are summarized in Table 1.

118 (1) We deployed 20 bubble traps in stream sections of about 100 m in length at three streams (60 traps in
119 total) for 30 days. Bubble traps consisted of an inverted plastic funnel (33.8 cm diameter, surface area
120 0.09 m^2), floating material (styrofoam) preventing traps from tilting in stream current, and a 60 ml plastic
121 luer-lock syringe with a three-way stopcock attached to the top of each funnel to allow sampling of the
122 trapped gas (Fig. S2). The traps were held in position by a string attached to stainless steel rods hammered
123 into the sediments. Traps were systematically deployed in the stream sections to cover a range of water
124 depths (0.1–0.9 m) and velocities ($0\text{--}0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). The volume of accumulated gas was recorded every 3-4
125 days and at least two samples were taken from each trap for later analysis of CH_4 concentrations of the
126 trapped bubbles. Details on CH_4 concentration analysis are given in the Supplementary Material: Analysis
127 of gas samples. We performed simulations of hypothetical sampling scenarios to determine the optimal
128 number of sampling days and number of bubble traps based on the generated data sets structured into
129 bins. All possible combinations of daily or trap ebullition averages were considered. Data analysis
130 followed the principles given by Wik et al. (2016), and details are given below.

131 (2.1) To assess the changes in concentration of CH_4 and $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CH}_4$ in trapped bubbles over time, two
132 bubble traps were placed in each of the two streams in a box with a full bottom (Fig. S3) immersed in the
133 stream water where water exchanged through two holes (50 cm^2) in the box to mimic in situ conditions.
134 We injected two different volumes of gas (50 ml and 150 ml) containing $\sim 60\%$ CH_4 into the traps.
135 Immediately after injections we sampled gas for later analysis of CH_4 concentration and $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CH}_4$ by
136 withdrawing 0.1 ml of gas with a gas-tight syringe and injecting it into a 12 ml vial (Labco, UK) that had
137 been previously flushed with synthetic air without hydrocarbons (Messer Technogas, CZ). The traps were
138 repeatedly sampled over a period of 13 to 18 days. We selected two different volumes of gas in order to
139 evaluate how the rate of change in concentration depends on its volume. The volumes used correspond
140 well to the bubble volumes recorded during our experiment on estimating the optimal number of traps, in
141 which the volumes after a few days were mostly in the range of a few tens to a few hundred millilitres.

142 (2.2) We verified the extent of syringe leakage by storing a gas mixture (natural bubble from sediment
143 with $\sim 50\%$ CH_4) in a syringe (130 ml) at room temperature ($22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for 40 days ($n = 1$). During this time,

144 we repeatedly sampled the gas from the syringe to analyze the CH₄ concentration and its isotopic
145 composition. The syringe was fitted with the same components as those used in the field experiment (a
146 three-way stopcock, an injection port and a hot melt adhesive sealing) to test the integrity of the entire
147 assembly.

148 (2.3) To estimate the contribution of CH₄ oxidation to the decrease of CH₄ in trapped bubbles, we
149 determined the specific fractionation factor (α) associated with CH₄ oxidation in stream water
150 experimentally and applied it to the model of isotope fractionation developed for a closed non-steady state
151 systems²⁴. Details of the experiment, related calculations and the ¹³C-CH₄ measurements are described in
152 the Supplementary Material.

153 (2.4) To estimate the effect of the redissolution of gas bubbles containing CH₄ after they enter the bubble
154 trap, we calculated the equilibration dynamics as described by Fick's first law of diffusion:

$$155 \quad \frac{dC_g}{dt} = -k \cdot \frac{A}{V_g} \cdot K_H \cdot (C_g - C_{eq})$$

156 where C_g is the partial pressure of methane in bubble (atm), t is the time (days), k is the gas transfer
157 coefficient for methane (m d⁻¹), A is the surface area of the gas-water exchange interface (m²), V_g is the
158 gas volume of accumulated gas in the bubble trap (ml), K_H is the temperature-dependent Henry's
159 solubility coefficient for methane (mol L⁻¹ atm⁻¹)²⁵, C_{eq} is equilibrium partial pressure of methane (atm).
160 The lower value of the gas transfer coefficient k (k = 0.1 m d⁻¹) was used, which corresponds to the
161 minimum effect of turbulence expected in our experimental setup^{26,27}.

162 (3) For CH₄ content comparison of naturally versus artificially released bubbles, we deployed six traps in
163 the stream one month before actual sampling. On the days of sampling, all traps were completely refilled
164 with stream water. We monitored the traps using binoculars from the stream bank. Immediately after a
165 bubble event spontaneously reached one of the traps, we collected a bubble sample from an inflatable
166 boat. Simultaneously, artificially released bubbles were sampled by manually disturbing the sediments
167 near the trap. Gas samples were measured for CH₄ concentration in the field and the remaining part of
168 each sample was stored in 12 ml vials (Labco, UK) for later analysis of $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$.

169

170 *Data analyses*

171 We simulated hypothetical sampling scenarios to determine the effect of the sampling period length and
172 the number of bubble traps on the uncertainty of CH₄ ebullition estimates. Based on this, we estimated the
173 minimum number of bubble traps and sampling days required to achieve ±20% of the mean for a total
174 number of traps or full sampling period. The ±20% is an arbitrary range of high accuracy in accordance
175 with previous studies^{14,15}. For each stream, we generated data sets structured into bins. The number of
176 bins corresponded to the maximum number of bubble traps (20) or sampling periods (10). All possible
177 combinations of sampling period or trap ebullition means were generated and included in each bin (i.e.
178 each possible number of bubble traps or sampling periods). The total number of unique combinations of a
179 selected subset of t traps is defined by the binomial coefficient $\binom{N}{t}$, where N represents the total number
180 of available traps. In this study, the maximum number of possible combinations was $\binom{20}{10} = 184,756$.
181 Thus, the first bin in each set represented one trap and included all possible outcomes (i.e. all trap-specific
182 ebullition means), and the last bin represented one possible outcome - the mean ebullition from the total
183 number of traps. The bins in between each consisted of all n combinations of trap ebullition averages,
184 with n increasing by $(n + 1)$ per bin. This represents how the possible outcomes (the uncertainty in
185 ebullition) converge towards the overall mean as the number of bubble traps increases. When all possible
186 combinations reached the threshold of ±20% of the average ebullition, the number of bubble traps was
187 assumed to be sufficient. The same approach was used for a temporal analysis to determine the optimal
188 number of sampling periods. Sampling was conducted at 3–4-day intervals, therefore, individual bins
189 represented sampling periods rather than individual days. Consequently, a total of ten bins were used to
190 represent the full 30-day measurement period. This analysis was performed using MATLAB software.
191 Additionally, we applied an asymptotic root mean square error (RMSE) model to extrapolate beyond the
192 maximum number of traps used in our study and estimate the optimal number of traps, independent of
193 sampling design limitations. This approach involves taking progressively larger subsamples ($n = 1000$

194 iterations per sample size) of the measured data for each stream to determine the optimal sampling effort.
195 The RMSE model predicted absolute and relative errors in mean CH₄ ebullition and identified the point at
196 which increasing the number of traps resulted in diminishing returns (e.g., when the expected deviation
197 from the mean fell below $\pm 20\%$). This analysis was conducted in R²⁸ using minpack.lm R package and
198 the nlsml function²⁹.

199 The differences in CH₄ concentration and $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ between naturally and artificially released bubbles
200 were tested using the Mann–Whitney rank sum test and Student's t-test, respectively. The relationship
201 between bubble volumes and their associated CH₄ content was evaluated using Spearman's correlation.

202

203 ***Results and discussion***

204 ***A wide variety of sampling designs for lotic CH₄ ebullition measurements across past studies***

205 We identified 42 studies measuring CH₄ ebullition from lotic aquatic ecosystems³⁰, mostly from the
206 Northern Hemisphere, primarily in North America, Europe, and China (Fig. 2a), reflecting a common
207 geographic bias in inland water greenhouse gas research³. Our extensive literature review showed that
208 floating chambers and bubble traps were used almost equally, accounting for 45% and 55%, respectively
209 (Fig. 2b). Although the mean number of replicates used to estimate CH₄ ebullition from individual studies
210 is comparable for bubble traps (7.6 ± 7.0) and floating chambers (5.8 ± 7.5), deployment times differ
211 considerably with 101 ± 126 days for bubble traps and 102 ± 325 minutes for floating chambers (mean \pm
212 SD; Fig. 3). The high variability across studies, as indicated by large standard deviations, underscores the
213 lack of standardized sampling designs for measuring fluvial CH₄ ebullition, and highlights the urgent
214 need for standardization. Additionally, trap and chamber sizes vary considerably, ranging from 0.008 to
215 0.79 m², across a variety of environments. This indicates that the number of traps or chambers alone does
216 not accurately reflect the spatial representativeness of measurements. The mean share of ebullition fluxes
217 to total CH₄ fluxes across all studies and methods used was $52 \pm 30\%$, which nicely corresponds to the

218 numbers found by Stanley et al.³. However, the share ranged from measuring zero fluxes up to 98%,
219 suggesting that CH₄ ebullition is a highly variable in streams and rivers.

220 *Accurate CH₄ ebullition estimates in highly heterogenous streams require larger number of bubble*
221 *traps than typically used*

222 Simulations from three different streams indicate that 12-24 days of measurements with at least 19 bubble
223 traps per stream achieve CH₄ ebullition estimates within 20% deviation of the mean (Fig. 4). Our results
224 suggest that fewer traps cause greater deviation from the mean than shorter deployment times (Fig. 4).
225 Our minimum trap estimate (n = 19) across all three streams overlaps with the maximum number of traps
226 used in our field measurements (n = 19-20). This suggests that our estimate may be constrained by the
227 sampling design. Nevertheless, it exceeds estimates by Robison et al.¹⁴ for streams (n = 10 based on 12
228 traps) or Wik et al.¹⁵ for northern lakes (n = 11 based on 17 traps), despite the relatively narrow widths of
229 our streams (2–20 m). Consistent with this, extrapolative validation of the asymptotic RMSE fit indicated
230 that achieving a deviation of less than 20% from the mean CH₄ ebullition would require substantially
231 more traps than were deployed in this study (43, 73, and 206 traps for the Hana, Jihlava, and
232 Schweinsbach, respectively). However, the asymptotic response curves suggest that most of the
233 uncertainty reduction is achieved with approximately 15–20 traps in our investigated streams. Beyond this
234 range, the curves approach an asymptote, and additional sampling effort yields only marginal reductions
235 in measurement uncertainty (Fig. S4). The substantially larger optimal trap estimate for Schweinsbach
236 can likely be attributed to the highly skewed distribution of CH₄ ebullition and its overall fluxes, which
237 were two orders of magnitude lower than in the other streams. Most traps recorded very low or zero
238 emissions, while total ebullition was dominated by two active spots.

239 The large variability in CH₄ ebullition likely stems from small-scale heterogeneities in the streams
240 associated with the drivers of ebullition (e.g. sediment characteristics, temperature, water depth, or flow
241 velocity)^{14,31,32}. Therefore, the representativeness of ebullition estimates appears to depend more on the
242 spatial heterogeneity of the examined ecosystem than on the specific number of traps. Taking the surface

243 area of the 100-metre-long stream sections into account, our sampling design recommended a number of
244 bubble traps that covered 0.1–0.8% of the total area examined. This corresponds well with the bubble
245 traps' spatial coverage of ~0.4 % (number derived from method description) recommended by Robison et
246 al.¹⁴ for small streams. Meanwhile, the recommended number of bubble traps for lakes (surface area
247 ranging from 1 to 17 ha) by Wik et al.¹⁵ corresponds to a considerably lower spatial coverage of 0.001–
248 0.02 % of the total lake area, which may reflect the expected lower small-scale spatial heterogeneity of
249 lake sediments compared to streams. Nevertheless, the recommended number of traps characterizes CH₄
250 ebullition in specific sections of the stream. Repeated measurements are required to ensure the
251 representativeness of the ebullition estimates if environmental conditions vary in other stream sections.

252 In our study, many of the accumulated gas samples in bubble traps (n = 87) collected within three days
253 contained <10% of CH₄ (Fig. S5). However, the concentrations were highly variable (0.01–67%), and
254 along with the bubble volume variability contributed significantly to the resulting variability in CH₄
255 ebullition from individual bubble traps. There was no consistent relationship between bubble volume and
256 CH₄ content across streams, with a positive correlation at Hana and Jihlava streams (r = 0.66 and 0.46, p
257 < 0.01) and no correlation at Schweinsbach stream (p > 0.4). The wide range of CH₄ content in the
258 bubbles, as well as the high occurrence of very low CH₄ contents, corresponds well with the previously
259 reported range of values (0.01–98%), with the lower CH₄ fractions mainly observed in sandy sediments
260 than in muck^{5,21,33}.

261 The recommended optimal number of traps was consistent across all three streams, but the optimal
262 sampling period length differed between streams. A recommended period of 12 or 18 days resulted from
263 streams with minimal water temperature changes over a month of trap deployment (18–20 °C and 20–24
264 °C, respectively). A longer period of 24 days was recommended for Schweinsbach stream where the first
265 attempt at measurement was thwarted by a flood event, and the subsequent deployment one month after
266 the flood had a water temperature range of 6–12 °C. We also could not exclude the effect of sediment
267 redeposition after the flood. The considerably longer optimum periods of 60 and 39 days estimated by

268 Robison et al.¹⁴ for streams and by Wik et al.¹⁵ for lakes, respectively, were based on sampling over four
269 months, where temperature changes likely influenced the temporal variability of CH₄ ebullition³⁴. In our
270 case, minimal water temperature changes over the entire 30-day period suggest that other factors drove
271 the temporal variability of ebullition. Short-term deployment of bubble traps is likely to miss short
272 episodes that trigger the sudden release of accumulated bubbles, for example due to pressure changes or
273 significant fluctuations in water depth^{35–37}. Therefore, the sampling period recommended based on our
274 experiments applies to a specific season. Longer campaigns or repetition in other seasons are essential for
275 annual ebullition estimates, especially in cases of significant temperature and water depth fluctuations
276 between seasons.

277 ***Bubble CH₄ loss from traps is primarily driven by redissolution, followed by microbial oxidation and***
278 ***syringe leakage***

279 Between 3 and 7% of the initial bubble CH₄ content was lost from traps per day and δ¹³C-CH₄ increased,
280 along with the decreasing concentration over time (Fig. 5). The CH₄ concentration decrease corresponds
281 to a first-order rate constant *k* ranging between 0.05 and 0.22 d⁻¹. The lower bubble CH₄ content and
282 enriched δ¹³C-CH₄ suggest redissolution of CH₄ (gas exchange between oversaturated syringe headspace
283 and underlying water) and the involvement of microbial oxidation in the removal of CH₄ from the traps.
284 The reduction in CH₄ concentration due to redissolution alone was estimated using a theoretical
285 calculation of diffusion, taking into account the size of the gas exchange interface and the volume of
286 inserted bubbles. This led to a 2.5–4% decrease in the initial CH₄ content per day, corresponding to a
287 first-order rate constant of 0.04 d⁻¹. On average, the redissolution accounted for 58 ± 12% of the observed
288 CH₄ loss from traps at the final phase of the experiment (Table S1).

289 To estimate the effect of CH₄ oxidation on the CH₄ decrease in trapped bubbles, we determined the CH₄
290 oxidation rate and the respective isotopic fractionation factor (αMOx) in both streams, where the
291 experiment was conducted. The CH₄ oxidation rate in water was 0.24 μg l⁻¹ h⁻¹ with αMOx = 1.037 in the
292 Hana stream and 1.8 μg l⁻¹ h⁻¹ with αMOx = 1.033 in the Kyjovka stream at in situ water temperatures of

293 19 and 21 °C, respectively. The experiment confirmed significant microbial CH₄ oxidation in the water
294 column, which also varied between streams. Furthermore, determining the site- and time-specific α MOx
295 minimized the largest source of uncertainty when calculating the extent of CH₄ oxidation based on
296 isotope mass balance. On average, CH₄ oxidation accounted for $33 \pm 15\%$ of the CH₄ removal from the
297 bubble traps at the final phase of the experiment, when the majority of CH₄ had been removed. The
298 estimated share of oxidation on overall CH₄ removal was higher in the Kyjovka stream (59 and 30%) than
299 in the Hana stream (27 and 17%). Since CH₄ oxidation occurs under the air-water interface, the partial
300 pressure of CH₄ in the underlying water is reduced. This increases the concentration gradient between the
301 syringe headspace and the water, which subsequently accelerates CH₄ redissolution. In accordance with
302 this, findings from lakes suggest that the estimate of CH₄ oxidation based on the same stable isotope
303 approach corresponds well with the difference in concentration between bubbles that have accumulated in
304 traps over a certain time period and bubbles that have been stirred manually ²². On the other hand,
305 contrasting results from a reservoir in which no change in CH₄ content in accumulated bubbles was
306 observed over 55 days ³⁸ suggest that environmental conditions or specific trap design features, such as
307 the gas-water interface area, can affect the rate at which CH₄ concentration changes in traps. Indeed, Kim
308 et al.³⁹ demonstrated that the original bubble gas composition and volume can be accurately modelled
309 using the measured gas concentrations at the end of deployment, alongside other relevant parameters such
310 as the surface area of the gas exchange interface, the gas-specific mass transfer coefficient, and the
311 temperature-dependent Henry's law solubility coefficient.

312 In addition, a minor part of the CH₄ concentration decrease can be explained by the syringe leakage. The
313 syringe leakage resulted in daily losses of 0.5% of the initial CH₄ content ($R^2 = 0.68$, $p < 0.05$). Applying
314 this decrease to our experimental data on changes in CH₄ content in trapped bubbles over time led to
315 syringe leakage accounting for an average of $14 \pm 4\%$ of total CH₄ removal at the final phase of the
316 experiment. Methane concentration decrease via leakage was associated with a shift in the $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ of
317 0.029‰ per day ($R^2 = 0.91$, $p < 0.05$; Fig. S6). The isotopic fractionation α for the syringe leakage was

318 1.007. This light isotope fractionation is likely associated with the diffusion of CH₄ through porous
319 material, which is also associated with partial discrimination of the heavier stable carbon isotope ¹³C⁴⁰. A
320 similar decrease in CH₄ concentrations associated with a shift in the δ¹³C-CH₄ was also reported during a
321 sample storage test, when CH₄ diffused through polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and polypropylene (PP)
322 plastic caps⁴¹. Nevertheless, the actual importance of CH₄ leakage may differ depending on the specific
323 material used for the bubble accumulation part, as well as on the bubble trap setup (whether it is under or
324 above the water). The most appropriate approach would therefore be to test the tightness of the specific
325 setup before measuring to correct any potential issues.

326 In summary, we found that redissolution was responsible for the majority of the decrease in CH₄
327 concentration in the trapped bubbles, followed by oxidation. Syringe leakage accounted for the smallest
328 proportion of the decrease. These three processes together explained 94–115% of the actual decrease in
329 CH₄ concentration observed in the bubble traps in our experiment. In accordance with the theoretical
330 assumptions of redissolution, the overall decrease in CH₄ concentration was faster in traps with smaller
331 bubble volumes (50 ml) than in traps with larger bubble volumes (150 ml) within both streams. Across
332 both streams, the decline in both traps was faster in the stream with higher CH₄ oxidation activity in the
333 water (Kyjovka) than in the one with lower CH₄ oxidation activity (Hana). This was consistent with
334 estimates of variable CH₄ loss due to oxidation based on the isotopic mass balance approach.

335 *Comparable CH₄ content and δ¹³C in natural and manually stirred bubbles*

336 Mean CH₄ concentration and δ¹³C-CH₄ in naturally and artificially released bubbles were not significantly
337 different with 65.1 ± 13.0 % and 64.8 ± 20.2 % (n = 12), and -67.1 ± 1.3 ‰ and -67.4 ± 1.4 ‰ (n = 16),
338 respectively (Fig. 6) (p = 0.665 and 0.585, respectively). The CH₄ content and δ¹³C-CH₄ of naturally
339 released bubbles and manually stirred bubbles from sediments have rarely been compared in literature.
340 We found a study by Martens and Chanton³⁰ that also reported minimal differences in CH₄ content of
341 bubbles obtained by these two sampling techniques in a coastal lagoon. Similarly, the same authors

342 compared bubbles sampled in a tidal freshwater estuary and observed no systematic difference in the
343 isotopic composition between these two bubble types⁴³.

344 *Towards a standardized stream ebullition assessment for accurate GHG estimates*

345 Our systematic review of previously adopted sampling designs in streams and rivers revealed high
346 variability in the methods used and the setup of bubble traps in particular. In light of our results, the short
347 deployment of floating chambers or the use of a very few bubble traps (< 5), which we found across
348 previous studies, might not adequately capture the high spatio-temporal variability of CH₄ ebullition in
349 streams. These findings also suggest that current estimates of fluvial CH₄ emissions remain highly
350 uncertain. For the estimation of fluvial CH₄ ebullition for a specific stream section and season, we
351 recommend the deployment of at least 19 bubble traps over a period of two to three weeks. Even though
352 we have doubled the number of traps recommended previously, our recommendation still reaches the
353 maximum number of traps used in our study design. Therefore, a robust sampling design mainly needs to
354 consider the large spatial heterogeneity of environmental parameters in streams (e.g. sediment
355 characteristics, flow velocity and water depth). Considering the high spatial variability of CH₄ content in
356 bubbles within the streams, we also strongly recommend trap-specific sampling of gas content conducted
357 shortly after bubble accumulation (within two to three days). Our experiments clearly demonstrate that
358 reducing the number of bubble traps results in a greater deviation in CH₄ ebullition estimates than
359 reducing the deployment time.

360 While the optimal number of traps and deployment time may vary with environmental heterogeneity,
361 other findings, such as the effect of CH₄ depletion processes in traps and the similarity between naturally
362 released and manually disturbed bubbles, can be applied when designing a sampling strategy in other
363 ecosystems. In particular, there is a risk of a rapid decrease in CH₄ concentration in the accumulated
364 bubbles over time, primarily due to CH₄ redissolution into the surrounding water and its oxidation, as
365 suggested by results of our experiments and supported by previous studies documenting decreasing CH₄
366 content in accumulated bubbles over prolonged sampling periods^{9,22}. Moreover, the composition of the

367 gas in the bubble can be further affected by the equilibration process of other gases present in the
368 surrounding water, such as nitrogen, oxygen, and carbon dioxide ³⁹. These processes depend on the size of
369 the trapped bubble and are more pronounced in small volumes. Therefore, if volumes of a few millilitres
370 are anticipated, the sampling strategy should be adapted to ensure prompt sampling. At the same time,
371 reducing the size of the gas-water exchange interface by modifying the trap design can minimize the
372 effects of redissolution and oxidation. Sampling fresh bubbles by sediment disturbance circumvents this
373 issue, but this method does not cover the high variability in CH₄ contents observed between traps,
374 resulting in potential over- or underestimation of CH₄ ebullition. Nevertheless, this approach can be used
375 as a complement, particularly for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -CH₄ analyses. Since ebullition is an episodic process, the entire
376 bubble volume is not expected to be trapped during the entire period. Therefore, a reasonable estimate of
377 the CH₄ content in accumulated bubbles can be obtained after two to three days. At sites with a high
378 probability of bubble accumulation within a short period of time, we recommend choosing a shorter gas
379 sampling interval to minimize CH₄ concentration changes.

380 Any correction to the original CH₄ content is specific to the trap design and environmental conditions.
381 The main process responsible for the majority of the decrease in CH₄ content in bubble traps is
382 redissolution, which can be modelled based on theoretical calculations for specific bubble volumes and
383 the size of the gas-water exchange interface. This is only challenged by the episodic nature of ebullition,
384 when it is difficult to derive the original CH₄ concentration in the trapped bubbles from the assumption of
385 a linear decrease over time, since the time of bubble release is unknown. However, Kim et al.³⁹ present a
386 modelling approach for deriving the original concentration of gas accumulated in bubble traps deployed
387 in Canadian lakes, based on the accumulation time of bubbles in traps that occurs most frequently. The
388 application of the same approach could be tested in highly heterogeneous conditions of small streams.
389 Moreover, high temporal resolution can be achieved by placing CH₄ sensors in floating chambers or
390 automated bubble traps with long deployment times ^{7,10,44,45}. For long-term deployment of the floating
391 chambers, the use of sensors to measure CH₄ concentrations seems necessary because considerable CH₄

392 oxidation and redissolution can be expected due to the large surface area of the gas-exchange interface.
393 The CH₄ sensors solve the issue of changing CH₄ concentration in the headspace over time, but a
394 sufficient number of chambers must be deployed across the study area to capture the considerable spatial
395 variability of ebullition. Assuming adequate coverage of stream heterogeneity by automatic traps
396 combined with sensors for accurate measurements of bubble volume and CH₄ concentration appears to be
397 the reliable approach, considering the CH₄ content changes observed in our experiments. However,
398 deploying automatic measuring systems may be more challenging in dynamic stream environments than
399 in lentic waters due to water depth and flow turbulence constraints.

400 All parameters tested in our experiments, including the number of traps, deployment length and the rate at
401 which CH₄ concentration changes in accumulated bubbles, may vary depending on the degree of
402 heterogeneity of the environment under investigation and may be time- and site-specific. Regardless of
403 the technique used, it is crucial to consider the large spatial and temporal variability of ebullition in highly
404 heterogeneous streams, as well as the possibility of rapid changes in CH₄ concentration in traps. The
405 sampling strategy must be adapted accordingly. Here, we present a comprehensive sampling procedure
406 based on estimates from field measurements at different conditions. Following this systematic approach
407 will increase the comparability of CH₄ ebullition estimates.

408 **Table 1.** Characteristics of the stream sites (mean \pm SD, if relevant) during the sampling period.

Parameter/Stream	CZ - Jihlava ¹	CZ - Hana ^{1,2}	CZ - Kyjovka ^{2,3}	AT - Schweinsbach ¹
GPS coordinates of the site	49.0261778N, 16.5187103E	49.2795372N, 17.0532986E	48.6824044N, 16.9372486E	48.1109167N, 15.3192222E
Strahler order	7	4	5	1
Geology	granite/gneiss	clay	sandstone/claystone	clastic sedimentary material
Trap deployment period ¹	25/6–25/7/2024	25/7–26/8/2024	na	16/10–15/11/2024
Box experiment period ²	na	29/7–20/8/2024	28/8–10/9/2024	na
Stream width (m)	19.5	5.5	15	2
Water depth (cm)	44.0 \pm 11.8	57.2 \pm 22.8	95.5 \pm 47.2	42.7 \pm 19.1
Stream velocity (m s ⁻¹)	0.2 \pm 0.1	0.03 \pm 0.03	0.1 \pm 0.04	0.1 \pm 0.1
pH	7.6 \pm 0.1	7.4 \pm 0.3	7.3 \pm 0.5	8.0 \pm 0.1
Conductivity (μ S cm ⁻¹)	519.4 \pm 31.6	880.9 \pm 68.4	619.6 \pm 5.0	641.8 \pm 19.5
Dissolved oxygen (mg L ⁻¹)	8.2 \pm 0.5	7.3 \pm 0.5	4.5 \pm 0.4	10.0 \pm 0.6
Dissolved oxygen (%)	95.7 \pm 3.8	80.2 \pm 6.8	52.1 \pm 5.9	89.8 \pm 7.0
Water Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	22.4 \pm 1.4	18.6 \pm 1.0	21.4 \pm 1.6	9.7 \pm 2.4
Dissolved CH ₄ (μ g L ⁻¹)	8.4 \pm 0.1	18.4 \pm 0.5	20.2 \pm 0.7	3.3 \pm 0.1
Catchment land use: forest/agriculture/urban/ rest (%)	28/66/5/1	31/62/7/0	27/64/7/1	16/84/0/0

409 ¹ streams, where the experiments for a number of the traps and length of the measurement period were
 410 conducted

411 ² streams, where the experiments on CH₄ concentrations changes within traps over time were conducted

412 ³ stream, where the comparison of naturally and artificially released bubbles was conducted

413

415

416 **Figure 1.** PRISMA diagram showing the results of the search strategy for studies assessing fluvial CH₄
 417 ebullition. Forty-one unique studies were included in the dataset based on the selection criteria, and one
 418 additional study that did not reference running waters in its title or abstract was added based on
 419 comparisons with the Global River Methane Database of concentrations and fluxes by Stanley et al.
 420 (2023) and our own collection.

421

422 **Figure 2.** (a) Global distribution of study sites where fluvial CH₄ ebullition was measured using bubble
 423 traps (brown) and floating chambers (blue) and (b) relative representation of ebullition methods across
 424 studies, differentiating between different types of floating chamber measurements (static versus drifting)
 425 and bubble CH₄ content methods (fresh = artificially stirred from sediments versus trapped bubbles).

426

427 **Figure 3.** (a) The lengths of the deployment time and (b) the number of replicated bubble traps or floating
 428 chambers used to estimate fluvial CH₄ ebullition across previous studies. The violin plots display Kernel
 429 density distributions, and the smaller black dots are the individual studies (differ between a and b as some
 430 studies did not report the number of replicate measurements, especially for floating chamber
 431 measurements). The bigger black dots and lines show the mean and standard deviation for each group.

432

433

434 **Figure 4.** Simulation of different sampling regimes showing the range of deviation from the standardized

435 CH₄ ebullition mean for different numbers of traps (a, c, e) and different numbers of sampling days (b, d,

436 f). Standardization was performed by dividing each individual measurement by the mean of the complete

437 dataset, resulting in a reference mean equal to 1. Red lines indicate 20% deviation from the standardized

438 mean (mean = 1). Each pair of panels (i.e., a-b, c-d, e-f) represents a different stream. Analyses were

439 performed by simulating all possible combinations of measurements. Note that the CH₄ ebullition

440 measurement of the last stream (e,f) was made one month after the flood event and at lower temperatures.

441
 442 **Figure 5.** Relative CH₄ content and its isotopic signature ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$) in bubble traps over time in the
 443 Haná stream (a, c) and the Kyjovka stream (b, d). The Kyjovka stream was characterized by a higher rate
 444 of CH₄ oxidation in water compared to the Hana stream. Bubble traps were filled with 50 ml and 150 ml
 445 of gas containing ~60% CH₄. The dashed lines show the decrease in CH₄ content that corresponds to the
 446 application of the first-order rate constant, which was derived from the observed decrease in CH₄
 447 concentration.

448

449 **Figure 6.** The comparison of CH₄ concentration (a) and its isotopic composition (b) between
 450 spontaneously released bubbles by ebullition and artificially released bubbles by sediment disturbance in
 451 the Kyjovka stream. The sampling was carried out on three dates from May to August 2024. The boxes
 452 represent the median (horizontal line inside boxes), the first and third quartiles (upper and lower boundary
 453 of the box), the 10th and 90th percentiles (whiskers), and the outliers outside the range of the 10th and
 454 90th percentiles (black dots).

455

456 **Acknowledgements**

457 We thank Gertraud Steniczka and Benjamin Misteli for their support during fieldwork. The research was
458 supported by Czech Science Foundation Grant No. 24-13457L, and by the Ministry of Education, Youth
459 and Sports of the Czech Republic (grant AdAgriF - Advanced methods of greenhouse gases emission
460 reduction and sequestration in agriculture and forest landscape for climate change mitigation
461 (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635)) and within the CzeCOS program, grant number LM2023048.
462 Further, this research was funded in part by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) [10.55776/I6922].

463

464 **Competing interests**

465 The authors declare no competing interests.

- 467 (1) Saunio, M.; Stavert, A. R.; Poulter, B.; Bousquet, P.; Canadell, J. G.; Jackson, R. B.; Raymond, P.
468 A.; Dlugokencky, E. J.; Houweling, S.; Patra, P. K.; Ciais, P.; Arora, V. K.; Bastviken, D.;
469 Bergamaschi, P.; Blake, D. R.; Brailsford, G.; Bruhwiler, L.; Carlson, K. M.; Carrol, M.; Castaldi,
470 S.; Chandra, N.; Crevoisier, C.; Crill, P. M.; Covey, K.; Curry, C. L.; Etiope, G.; Frankenberg, C.;
471 Gedney, N.; Hegglin, M. I.; Höglund-Isaksson, L.; Hugelius, G.; Ishizawa, M.; Ito, A.; Janssens-
472 Maenhout, G.; Jensen, K. M.; Joos, F.; Kleinen, T.; Krummel, P. B.; Langenfelds, R. L.; Laruelle,
473 G. G.; Liu, L.; Machida, T.; Maksyutov, S.; McDonald, K. C.; McNorton, J.; Miller, P. A.; Melton,
474 J. R.; Morino, I.; Müller, J.; Murguia-Flores, F.; Naik, V.; Niwa, Y.; Noce, S.; O’Doherty, S.;
475 Parker, R. J.; Peng, C.; Peng, S.; Peters, G. P.; Prigent, C.; Prinn, R.; Ramonet, M.; Regnier, P.;
476 Riley, W. J.; Rosentreter, J. A.; Segers, A.; Simpson, I. J.; Shi, H.; Smith, S. J.; Steele, L. P.;
477 Thornton, B. F.; Tian, H.; Tohjima, Y.; Tubiello, F. N.; Tsuruta, A.; Viovy, N.; Voulgarakis, A.;
478 Weber, T. S.; van Weele, M.; van der Werf, G. R.; Weiss, R. F.; Worthy, D.; Wunch, D.; Yin, Y.;
479 Yoshida, Y.; Zhang, W.; Zhang, Z.; Zhao, Y.; Zheng, B.; Zhu, Q.; Zhu, Q.; Zhuang, Q. The Global
480 Methane Budget 2000–2017. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **2020**, *12* (3), 1561–1623.
481 <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-1561-2020>.
- 482 (2) Rocher-Ros, G.; Stanley, E. H.; Loken, L. C.; Casson, N. J.; Raymond, P. A.; Liu, S.; Amatulli, G.;
483 Sponseller, R. A. Global Methane Emissions from Rivers and Streams. *Nature* **2023**.
484 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06344-6>.
- 485 (3) Stanley, E. H.; Loken, L. C.; Casson, N. J.; Oliver, S. K.; Sponseller, R. A.; Wallin, M. B.; Zhang,
486 L.; Rocher-Ros, G. GRiMeDB: The Global River Methane Database of Concentrations and Fluxes.
487 *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **2023**, *15* (7), 2879–2926. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-2879-2023>.
- 488 (4) Crawford, J. T.; Stanley, E. H. Controls on Methane Concentrations and Fluxes in Streams Draining
489 Human-Dominated Landscapes. *Ecol. Appl.* **2016**, *26* (5), 1581–1591. <https://doi.org/10.1890/15-1330>.
- 491 (5) Michaelis, T.; Kaplar, F.; Baumann, T.; Wunderlich, A.; Einsiedl, F. High Methane Ebullition
492 throughout One Year in a Regulated Central European Stream. *Sci. Rep.* **2024**, *14* (1), 5359.
493 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-54760-z>.
- 494 (6) Sø, J. S.; Sand-Jensen, K.; Kragh, T. Self-Made Equipment for Automatic Methane Diffusion and
495 Ebullition Measurements From Aquatic Environments. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **2024**, *129*
496 (6), e2024JG008035. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JG008035>.
- 497 (7) Olsen, B. W.; Kragh, T.; Sø, J. S.; Polauke, E.; Sand-Jensen, K. Environmental Drivers of Seasonal
498 and Hourly Fluxes of Methane and Carbon Dioxide across a Lowland Stream Network with Mixed
499 Catchment. *Biogeochemistry* **2025**, *168* (1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-024-01205-4>.
- 500 (8) Ran, L.; Shi, H.; Yang, X. Magnitude and Drivers of CO₂ and CH₄ Emissions from an
501 Arid/Semiarid River Catchment on the Chinese Loess Plateau. *J. Hydrol.* **2021**, *598*, 126260.
502 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126260>.
- 503 (9) Wik, M.; Crill, P. M.; Varner, R. K.; Bastviken, D. Multiyear Measurements of Ebullitive Methane
504 Flux from Three Subarctic Lakes. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **2013**, *118* (3), 1307–1321.
505 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrg.20103>.
- 506 (10) Maher, D. T.; Drexler, M.; Tait, D. R.; Johnston, S. G.; Jeffrey, L. C. iAMES: An iNexpensive, A
507utomated M Ethane E Bullition S Ensor. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2019**, *53* (11), 6420–6426.
508 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b01881>.
- 509 (11) Marcon, L.; Bleninger, T.; Männich, M.; Hilgert, S. High-Frequency Measurements of Gas
510 Ebullition in a Brazilian Subtropical Reservoir—Identification of Relevant Triggers and Seasonal
511 Patterns. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* **2019**, *191* (6), 357. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-019-7498-9>.
- 512 (12) Wilkinson, J.; Maeck, A.; Alshboul, Z.; Lorke, A. Continuous Seasonal River Ebullition
513 Measurements Linked to Sediment Methane Formation. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *49* (22),
514 13121–13129. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b01525>.

- 515 (13) Wilcock, R. J.; Sorrell, B. K. Emissions of Greenhouse Gases CH₄ and N₂O from Low-Gradient
516 Streams in Agriculturally Developed Catchments. *Water, Air, Soil Pollut.* **2008**, *188* (1–4), 155–
517 170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-007-9532-8>.
- 518 (14) Robison, A. L.; Wollheim, W. M.; Turek, B.; Bova, C.; Snay, C.; Varner, R. K. Spatial and
519 Temporal Heterogeneity of Methane Ebullition in Lowland Headwater Streams and the Impact on
520 Sampling Design. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **2021**, *66* (12), 4063–4076. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.11943>.
- 521 (15) Wik, M.; Thornton, B. F.; Bastviken, D.; Uhlbäck, J.; Crill, P. M. Biased Sampling of Methane
522 Release from Northern Lakes: A Problem for Extrapolation. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **2016**, *43* (3), 1256–
523 1262. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL066501>.
- 524 (16) Wang, G.; Xia, X.; Liu, S.; Zhang, L.; Zhang, S.; Wang, J.; Xi, N.; Zhang, Q. Intense Methane
525 Ebullition from Urban Inland Waters and Its Significant Contribution to Greenhouse Gas Emissions.
526 *Water Res.* **2021**, *189*, 116654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116654>.
- 527 (17) Chen, S.; Wang, D.; Ding, Y.; Yu, Z.; Liu, L.; Li, Y.; Yang, D.; Gao, Y.; Tian, H.; Cai, R.; Chen, Z.
528 Ebullition Controls on CH₄ Emissions in an Urban, Eutrophic River: A Potential Time-Scale Bias
529 in Determining the Aquatic CH₄ Flux. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2021**, *55* (11), 7287–7298.
530 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c00114>.
- 531 (18) Ostrovsky, I.; McGinnis, D. F.; Lapidus, L.; Eckert, W. Quantifying Gas Ebullition with
532 Echosounder: The Role of Methane Transport by Bubbles in a Medium-Sized Lake: Measuring
533 Methane Transport with Bubbles. *Limnol. Oceanogr. Methods* **2008**, *6* (2), 105–118.
534 <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2008.6.105>.
- 535 (19) DelSontro, T.; McGinnis, D. F.; Wehrli, B.; Ostrovsky, I. Size Does Matter: Importance of Large
536 Bubbles and Small-Scale Hot Spots for Methane Transport. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *49* (3),
537 1268–1276. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es5054286>.
- 538 (20) Maeck, A.; DelSontro, T.; McGinnis, D. F.; Fischer, H.; Flury, S.; Schmidt, M.; Fietzek, P.; Lorke,
539 A. Sediment Trapping by Dams Creates Methane Emission Hot Spots. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2013**,
540 *47* (15), 8130–8137. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es4003907>.
- 541 (21) Crawford, J. T.; Stanley, E. H.; Spawn, S. A.; Finlay, J. C.; Loken, L. C.; Striegl, R. G. Ebullitive
542 Methane Emissions from Oxygenated Wetland Streams. *Glob. Change Biol.* **2014**, *20* (11), 3408–
543 3422. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12614>.
- 544 (22) Thottathil, S. D.; Prairie, Y. T. Coupling of Stable Carbon Isotopic Signature of Methane and
545 Ebullitive Fluxes in Northern Temperate Lakes. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2021**, *777*, 146117.
546 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146117>.
- 547 (23) Page, M. J.; McKenzie, J. E.; Bossuyt, P. M.; Boutron, I.; Hoffmann, T. C.; Mulrow, C. D.;
548 Shamseer, L.; Tetzlaff, J. M.; Akl, E. A.; Brennan, S. E.; Chou, R.; Glanville, J.; Grimshaw, J. M.;
549 Hróbjartsson, A.; Lalu, M. M.; Li, T.; Loder, E. W.; Mayo-Wilson, E.; McDonald, S.; McGuinness,
550 L. A.; Stewart, L. A.; Thomas, J.; Tricco, A. C.; Welch, V. A.; Whiting, P.; Moher, D. The
551 PRISMA 2020 Statement: An Updated Guideline for Reporting Systematic Reviews. *BMJ* **2021**,
552 *n71*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
- 553 (24) Liptay, K.; Chanton, J.; Czepiel, P.; Mosher, B. Use of Stable Isotopes to Determine Methane
554 Oxidation in Landfill Cover Soils. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* **1998**, *103* (D7), 8243–8250.
555 <https://doi.org/10.1029/97JD02630>.
- 556 (25) Sander, R. Compilation of Henry’s Law Constants (Version 4.0) for Water as Solvent. *Atmospheric*
557 *Chem. Phys.* **2015**, *15* (8), 4399–4981. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-4399-2015>.
- 558 (26) Wanninkhof, R. Relationship between Wind Speed and Gas Exchange over the Ocean Revisited:
559 Gas Exchange and Wind Speed over the Ocean. *Limnol. Oceanogr. Methods* **2014**, *12* (6), 351–362.
560 <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2014.12.351>.
- 561 (27) Holgerson, M. A.; Farr, E. R.; Raymond, P. A. Gas Transfer Velocities in Small Forested Ponds. *J.*
562 *Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **2017**, *122* (5), 1011–1021. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JG003734>.
- 563 (28) R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing, 2025. [https://www.R-](https://www.R-project.org/)
564 [project.org/](https://www.R-project.org/).

- 565 (29) Timur V. Elzhov, Katharine M. Mullen, Andrej-Nikolai Spiess, Ben Bolker. Minpack.Lm: R
566 Interface to the Levenberg-Marquardt Nonlinear Least-Squares Algorithm Found in MINPACK,
567 Plus Support for Bounds, 2022, 1.2-4. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.minpack.lm>.
- 568 (30) Bednarik, A.; Darenova, E.; Cvetkovic, H.; Doebke, C.; Karwautz, C.; Kowalska, N.; Kokrda, L.;
569 Attermeyer, K. Chasing Bubbles: Towards a Standardized Approach for Quantifying Methane
570 Ebullition in Streams and Rivers, [Data set]. Zenodo. 2026.
571 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18743758>.
- 572 (31) Baulch, H. M.; Dillon, P. J.; Maranger, R.; Schiff, S. L. Diffusive and Ebullitive Transport of
573 Methane and Nitrous Oxide from Streams: Are Bubble-Mediated Fluxes Important? *J. Geophys.*
574 *Res.* **2011**, *116* (G4), G04028. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JG001656>.
- 575 (32) Bednarik, A.; Bodmer, P.; Darenova, E.; Kokrda, L.; Pavelka, M. Temperature, Water Depth, and
576 Flow Velocity Are Important Drivers of Methane Ebullition in a Temperate Lowland Stream. *J.*
577 *Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **2024**, *129* (5), e2023JG007597.
578 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JG007597>.
- 579 (33) Baulch, H. M.; Dillon, P. J.; Maranger, R.; Schiff, S. L. Diffusive and Ebullitive Transport of
580 Methane and Nitrous Oxide from Streams: Are Bubble-Mediated Fluxes Important? *J. Geophys.*
581 *Res.* **2011**, *116* (G4), G04028. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JG001656>.
- 582 (34) Aben, R. C. H.; Barros, N.; van Donk, E.; Frenken, T.; Hilt, S.; Kazanjian, G.; Lamers, L. P. M.;
583 Peeters, E. T. H. M.; Roelofs, J. G. M.; de Senerpont Domis, L. N.; Stephan, S.; Velthuis, M.; Van
584 de Waal, D. B.; Wik, M.; Thornton, B. F.; Wilkinson, J.; DelSontro, T.; Kosten, S. Cross
585 Continental Increase in Methane Ebullition under Climate Change. *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8* (1), 1682.
586 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-01535-y>.
- 587 (35) Maeck, A.; Hofmann, H.; Lorke, A. Pumping Methane out of Aquatic Sediments – Ebullition
588 Forcing Mechanisms in an Impounded River. *Biogeosciences* **2014**, *11* (11), 2925–2938.
589 <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-2925-2014>.
- 590 (36) Wang, G.; Xia, X.; Liu, S.; Zhang, L.; Zhang, S.; Wang, J.; Xi, N.; Zhang, Q. Intense Methane
591 Ebullition from Urban Inland Waters and Its Significant Contribution to Greenhouse Gas Emissions.
592 *Water Res.* **2021**, *189*, 116654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116654>.
- 593 (37) Zhang, L.; Xia, X.; Liu, S.; Zhang, S.; Li, S.; Wang, J.; Wang, G.; Gao, H.; Zhang, Z.; Wang, Q.;
594 Wen, W.; Liu, R.; Yang, Z.; Stanley, E. H.; Raymond, P. A. Significant Methane Ebullition from
595 Alpine Permafrost Rivers on the East Qinghai–Tibet Plateau. *Nat. Geosci.* **2020**, *13* (5), 349–354.
596 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-020-0571-8>.
- 597 (38) Harrison, J. A.; Deemer, B. R.; Birchfield, M. K.; O’Malley, M. T. Reservoir Water-Level
598 Drawdowns Accelerate and Amplify Methane Emission. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2017**, *51* (3), 1267–
599 1277. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b03185>.
- 600 (39) Kim, J.; Thottathil, S. D.; Prairie, Y. T. A Simple Approach to Quantifying Whole-lake Methane
601 Ebullition and Sedimentary Methane Production, and Its Application to the Canadian Lake Pulse
602 Dataset. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **2025**, *70* (2), 393–410. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.12767>.
- 603 (40) De Visscher, A.; De Pourcq, I.; Chanton, J. Isotope Fractionation Effects by Diffusion and Methane
604 Oxidation in Landfill Cover Soils. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* **2004**, *109* (D18), 2004JD004857.
605 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JD004857>.
- 606 (41) Li, W.; Lu, S.; Li, J.; Feng, W.; Zhang, P.; Wang, J.; Wang, Z.; Li, X. Concentration Loss and
607 Diffusive Fractionation of Methane during Storage: Implications for Gas Sampling and Isotopic
608 Analysis. *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *101*, 104562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2022.104562>.
- 609 (42) Martens, C. S.; Chanton, J. P. Radon as a Tracer of Biogenic Gas Equilibration and Transport from
610 Methane-saturated Sediments. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* **1989**, *94* (D3), 3451–3459.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1029/JD094iD03p03451>.
- 612 (43) Chanton, J. P.; Martens, C. S. Seasonal Variations in Ebullitive Flux and Carbon Isotopic
613 Composition of Methane in a Tidal Freshwater Estuary. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* **1988**, *2* (3),
614 289–298. <https://doi.org/10.1029/GB002i003p00289>.

- 615 (44) Sørensen, J. S.; Martinsen, K. T.; Kragh, T.; Sand-Jensen, K. Hourly Methane and Carbon Dioxide Fluxes
616 from Temperate Ponds. *Biogeochemistry* **2024**, *167* (2), 177–195. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-024-01124-4)
617 [024-01124-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-024-01124-4).
- 618 (45) Varadharajan, C.; Hermosillo, R.; Hemond, H. F. A Low-Cost Automated Trap to Measure
619 Bubbling Gas Fluxes: Measuring Methane Ebullition. *Limnol. Oceanogr. Methods* **2010**, *8* (7), 363–
620 375. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2010.8.363>.
621

1 **Supplementary material for**

2 **Chasing bubbles: towards a standardized approach for quantifying methane**
3 **ebullition using bubble traps in streams and rivers**

4
5 *Adam Bednarik^{1*}, Eva Darenova¹, Helena Cvetkovic², Charlotte Doebke^{2,3}, Clemens Karwautz², Lukas*
6 *Kokrda¹, Natalia Kowalska¹, & Katrin Attermeyer^{2,3}*

7 *¹ Department of Matters and Energy Fluxes, Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences,*
8 *Belidla 4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic*

9 *² Department of Functional and Evolutionary Ecology, University of Vienna, Djerassiplatz 1, 1030 Vienna, Austria*

10 *³ WasserCluster Lunz- Biologische Station, Dr. Carl Kupelwieser Promenade 5, 3293 Lunz am See, Austria*

11
12 *Corresponding author: Adam Bednarik (bednarik.a@czechglobe.cz)

21 **Supplementary Methods**

22 *Details of systematic review of the sampling designs*

23 We searched for papers measuring and reporting methane (CH₄) ebullition from running waters. The
24 relevant papers were obtained from two different sources: a systematic review and private and online
25 databases. We used the standardized “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-
26 Analyses” (PRISMA) method to select studies to be included in the dataset (Page et al. 2021). The
27 following inclusion criteria were defined: (i) to be published in English with (ii) original data and hence,
28 reviews and other meta-analyses were excluded; (iii) to be performed in all types of streams and rivers,
29 creeks or brooks and hence, reservoirs and standing water bodies as well as marine ecosystems were
30 excluded; (iv) to include a method to measure or calculate methane ebullition and hence, papers only
31 measuring diffusive or plant-mediated fluxes were excluded (Fig. S1). The search revealed papers in
32 reservoirs, and we included these papers when they contained a fluvial site according to the site
33 descriptions in the method sections of the papers (4 papers). The search also revealed three papers done in
34 ditches, where CH₄ ebullition was measured, and we included these papers, too.

35 **Figure S1.** Initial title, abstract, and keywords (a) and full-text screening (b) decision trees for the list of
36 studies assessing fluvial CH₄ ebullition.
37

38 For the systematic literature review, studies on fluvial CH₄ ebullition were identified through a
39 comprehensive search of Web of Science and Scopus on November 29, 2024 using the following
40 keywords limited to title and abstract: ((methan* OR ch4) AND (ebulli* OR bubbl* OR degas* OR
41 outgas* OR flux* OR emission*) AND (stream* OR river* OR creek* OR brook* OR "flowing water*" OR "running water*" OR fluvial* OR lotic*)) and English (Languages); excluding subject areas Social,
42 Economic, Medical or Computer Sciences). Keyword selection was based and refined on pilot screening
43 and a comparison of studies collected by Adam Bednarik assessing CH₄ ebullition from streams.

44
45 The Web of Science and Scopus search identified 3,659 records after exclusion of 1,468 duplicate studies.
46 Study titles and abstracts were skimmed for relevance, and we excluded 3,347 records that did not meet
47 our inclusion criteria. Then, we excluded 271 records via full-text reviews based on the selection criteria
48 previously described, leaving 41 unique studies for the dataset. From comparisons with the Global River
49 Methane Database of concentrations and fluxes by Stanley et al. (2023) and our own collection, we added
50 one more study that did not use any reference to running waters in their title or abstract (Herrero Ortega et
51 al. 2019). From these studies, we extracted the description of the sampling method (including the number
52 of traps or floating chamber incubations and the description of the method) as well as the share of CH₄
53 ebullition flux to total CH₄ flux directly from text, tables or by digitizing information from plots using
54 WebPlotDigitizer software v.3.4 (Rohatgi 2020). For each study, we also extracted additional information
55 related to geographic location, stream type and other descriptives such as stream order, width, watershed
56 area, flow velocity and discharge, as well as sampling year and period (sampling year and mainly month
57 within the sampling year). For the geographical coordinates, we provided site-specific values if available
58 in the papers, but for studies conducted over large areas we provided an average latitude and longitude
59 value. For the share of ebullition fluxes to total CH₄ fluxes, we averaged per study. In addition, we took
60 the middle number if a range was given for the length of the deployment period and the replicate number
61 of chambers or traps used to obtain one value for the figures. The full table is available in the Zenodo data
62 repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15687421> (Bednarik et al. 2025).

63 *Analysis of gas samples*

64 We sampled the gas from bubble traps by withdrawing 15–20 ml of gas via the three-way stopcock at the
65 top of the bubble trap using a 20 ml luer lock plastic syringe. Samples were injected into a 12 ml vial
66 (Labco, UK) that had been previously flushed with zero air and pre-evacuated. The gas samples were
67 analyzed for CH₄ concentration with a cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) gas concentration analyzer
68 (Picarro GasScouter G4301, Picarro, CA, USA) and an ultraportable greenhouse gas analyzer (UGGA,
69 Los Gatos Research, Inc., USA) using a closed-loop approach (Wilkinson et al. 2018). This method
70 calculates the CH₄ concentration in the original sample based on the change in concentration after the
71 sample injection into the closed loop created between the gas inlet and outlet of the analyzer. Depending
72 on the expected concentration of CH₄, 0.01, 0.1, 0.5 or 1 ml of the sample was withdrawn from the vial
73 using a gas-tight syringe (Hamilton, Switzerland) and injected into the closed-loop system. The CH₄
74 concentration was then calculated as follows:

$$75 \quad CH_{4_sam} = \frac{V_{eff} \times \Delta CH_4 + V_{sam} \times CH_{4_post}}{V_{sam}} \quad (1)$$

76 where CH_{4_sam} represents CH₄ concentration in the sample, ΔCH_4 is the difference between the
77 background CH₄ concentration in the loop before the injection and the equilibrium CH₄ concentration
78 after the sample injection, V_{sam} is the volume of the injected into the loop, CH_{4_post} is the equilibrium
79 CH₄ concentration in the loop after the sample injection, and V_{eff} is the effective volume of the closed
80 loop.

81 The effective volume of the closed loop (V_{eff}) was estimated by injecting a calibration gas (Messer,
82 Germany) with a known CH₄ concentration of 102.8, 1,001, 17,600 ppm or 99.99%, depending on the
83 sample concentration and volume, in several replicates alongside each set of samples, and calculated as
84 follows:

$$85 \quad V_{eff} = \frac{V_{cal} \times (CH_{4_cal} - CH_{4_post})}{\Delta CH_4} \quad (2)$$

86 where V_{cal} is the volume of calibration gas injected into the loop, CH_4_{cal} is known CH_4 concentration of
87 calibration gas, $\text{CH}_4_{\text{post}}$ is the equilibrium CH_4 concentration in the loop after the sample injection, and
88 ΔCH_4 is the difference between the background CH_4 concentration in the loop before the injection and the
89 equilibrium CH_4 concentration after the sample injection.

90 Subsamples for stable isotopic composition of CH_4 ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$) analysis were taken from the same vials
91 that were previously measured for concentrations as described above. Gas samples were analyzed in the
92 laboratory using a cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) analyzer (G2201-i, Picarro Inc, USA) equipped
93 with a Small sample introduction module (SSIM2, Picarro Inc, USA) to determine $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$. Samples
94 with high CH_4 concentration were diluted using hydrocarbon-free ultrapure zero air (Messer Technogas,
95 CZ) to stay within the measurement guaranteed range of the analyzer and close to the concentration of
96 standards used. The calibration of $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ was performed using certified isotopic standards ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4 =$
97 $-68.6 \pm 0.3\text{‰}$, $-45.5 \pm 0.3\text{‰}$, and $-25.8 \pm 0.3\text{‰}$; Airgas, USA) and the measurements were corrected for
98 instrumental drift during the measurement time using the same standards. The CH_4 isotopic data are
99 reported in the standard delta notation (δ) expressed in ‰ relative to the Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite
100 standard.

101 *Description of an incubation experiment to determine the fractionation factor (α) associated with CH₄*
102 *oxidation in stream water*

103 At two streams (CZ-Kyjovka, CZ-Hana), a set of eight 50 mL glass vials was filled with surface water
104 (sampled 10 cm below the water surface), sealed with a butyl stopper and crimped with an aluminum cap.
105 Two vials were immediately treated with 200 μ L of 25% H₂SO₄ injected through the butyl stopper to
106 prevent further microbial activity. These two vials corresponded to the initial surface water CH₄
107 concentration at the start of the incubation. The remaining vials were incubated in situ and the incubation
108 was stopped by adding 200 μ L of 25% H₂SO₄ to duplicate vials at three time intervals in the range of 0-24
109 h after the start of the incubation. Water samples were analyzed for dissolved CH₄ concentration using the
110 headspace equilibration method, and subsamples of the headspace were stored in 12 ml vials (Labco, UK)
111 for later analysis of $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$.

112 The α values were calculated using a simplified Rayleigh fractionation model for a closed system
113 (Mariotti et al. 1981):

$$114 \ln\left(\frac{\text{CH}_4}{\text{CH}_{4_initial}}\right) = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \ln\left(\frac{1000+\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4}{1000+\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_{4_initial}}\right) \quad (3)$$

115 where CH₄ and $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ are the concentration and isotopic signature of the CH₄ in the headspace at
116 subsequent time points, and CH₄_initial and $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ _initial are the concentration and isotopic signature
117 of the CH₄ at the beginning of the incubation.

118 The α value was derived using a fractionation model for a closed system, given that the experiment was
119 conducted in crimped vials, preventing any exchange of substances with the surrounding water. The α
120 was obtained by plotting Eq. (3) with $\ln(1000 + \delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4)$ on the X axis and $\ln(\text{CH}_4)$ on the Y axis for a
121 series of time points and performing a linear regression with a slope of $\alpha/(1 - \alpha)$ as described by
122 Mahieu et al. (2006).

123

124 The relative extent of CH₄ oxidation in bubble traps was estimated by a model of isotope fractionation
125 developed for a closed steady state systems (Liptay et al. 1998): :

$$126 \ln(1 - f_{ox}) = [ln(\delta^{13}C-CH_{4_source} + 1000) - ln(\delta^{13}C-CH_4 + 1000)]/(\alpha - 1) \quad (4)$$

127 where f_{ox} is the fraction of CH₄ oxidized, $\delta^{13}C-CH_4$ is a subsequent isotopic signature of CH₄ in traps at
128 different times of experiment, $\delta^{13}C-CH_{4_source}$ is an isotopic signature of original CH₄, which was
129 injected into the traps, α is the isotopic fractionation factor for CH₄ oxidation (eq. 3).

130 **Table S1.** Estimated fraction of CH₄ removal by individual processes during the bubble trap experiment.

131 The last column shows the actual CH₄ removal based on the decrease in measured CH₄ concentration (1 =

132 100%).

Site/Bubble volume (ml)	Time (h)	Redissolution	Oxidation	Leakage	Redissolution + Oxidation + Leakage	Measured CH ₄ loss
CZ - Hana 50 ml	16	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.08
	40	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.18
	64	0.11	0.01	0.02	0.13	0.28
	160	0.24	0.01	0.05	0.30	0.55
	256	0.36	0.16	0.07	0.59	0.72
	426	0.52	0.24	0.12	0.88	0.88
CZ - Hana 150 ml	16	0.02	0.00	0.005	0.03	0.03
	40	0.06	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.08
	64	0.09	0.00	0.02	0.11	0.13
	160	0.21	0.005	0.05	0.26	0.29
	256	0.31	0.06	0.07	0.45	0.43
	426	0.47	0.11	0.12	0.69	0.60
CZ - Kyjovka 50 ml	26	0.04	0.003	0.01	0.06	0.21
	53	0.09	0.005	0.02	0.11	0.38
	119	0.19	0.15	0.03	0.37	0.66
	174	0.27	0.23	0.05	0.55	0.80
	311	0.43	0.55	0.09	1.07	0.94
CZ - Kyjovka 150 ml	26	0.04	0.005	0.01	0.05	0.10
	53	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.11	0.20
	119	0.16	0.07	0.03	0.27	0.40
	174	0.23	0.12	0.05	0.40	0.52
	311	0.38	0.22	0.09	0.69	0.73

133 * During the experiment, the proportion of CH₄ removal explained by the monitored processes increased,
 134 reaching 94–115% of the measured CH₄ decrease in the final phase: compare the fraction removed by all
 135 three processes (Redissolution + Oxidation + Leakage) and the measured CH₄ loss. The lower proportion
 136 of CH₄ removal explained by these three processes in the initial phases is probably due to small absolute
 137 changes in CH₄ concentration and its isotopic composition, which led to uncertainty in estimating the
 138 relative proportions of oxidation and dissolution.

139

140

141 **Figure S2.** Example of bubble traps deployment covering a range of water depths and velocities in the
142 Schweinsbach (top left) and Hana (top right) streams. To measure CH₄ ebullitive fluxes, a bubble trap
143 consisting of an inverted plastic funnel (diameter: 33.8 cm; surface area: 0.09 m²), floating material
144 (Styrofoam) and a 60 ml plastic Luer-lock syringe with a three-way stopcock was used (bottom left).
145 Another bubble trap design, using the same materials, was employed for deployment in very shallow
146 zones (bottom right). The bubble trap was submerged by only a few centimetres (2–3 cm) to avoid
147 disturbing the sediment.

148

149 **Figure S3.** Picture of a box with a full bottom in a stream, where two bubble traps were placed to
150 determine any potential changes in CH₄ concentration and its isotopic composition in trapped bubbles
151 over time. The box was immersed in the stream water to keep the environmental conditions in situ (e.g.
152 water and air temperature, pressure or microbial CH₄ oxidation). Water could exchange through two holes
153 (50 cm²) in the box, but naturally released bubbles could not reach the traps due to the full bottom of the
154 box. The experiment was carried out in two streams (CZ-Hana, CZ-Kyjovka).

155 **Supplementary Results**

156

157 **Figure S4.** Development of relative precision (% of the mean) of CH₄ ebullition estimates with increasing
158 numbers of bubble traps based on an asymptotic root mean square error (RMSE) model. Solid lines
159 represent the asymptotic fits for individual streams. Dashed horizontal lines indicate target precision
160 levels ranging from 10 to 50% of the mean. The intersection between the fitted curves and the 20% target
161 precision line corresponds to 43, 73, and 206 traps for the Hana, Jihlava, and Schweinsbach, respectively.

162

163

164 **Figure S5.** Histogram of the content of CH₄ in the samples of gas accumulated in the bubble traps (n =
165 117).

166

167 **Figure S6.** Changes in the concentration of CH₄ (a) and in its isotopic composition (b) in the closed
 168 syringe that was left at room temperature for 40 days. We used the same type of syringe that was used to
 169 make the bubble traps, as well as the glue, three-way valve and injection port.

170

171 **Supplementary References**

- 172 Bednařík, A., E. Darenova, H. Cvetkovic, C. Doebke, C. Karwautz, N. Kowalska, L. Kokrda, and K.
173 Attermeyer. 2026. Chasing bubbles: towards a standardized approach for quantifying methane
174 ebullition in streams and rivers [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18743758>
- 175 Herrero Ortega, S., C. Romero González-Quijano, P. Casper, G. A. Singer, and M. O. Gessner. 2019.
176 Methane emissions from contrasting urban freshwaters: Rates, drivers, and a whole-city footprint.
177 *Glob. Change Biol.* **25**: 4234–4243. doi:10.1111/gcb.14799
- 178 Liptay, K., J. Chanton, P. Czepiel, and B. Mosher. 1998. Use of stable isotopes to determine methane
179 oxidation in landfill cover soils. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres* **103**: 8243–8250.
180 doi:10.1029/97JD02630
- 181 Mahieu, K., A. D. Visscher, P. A. Vanrolleghem, and O. V. Cleemput. 2006. Carbon and hydrogen
182 isotope fractionation by microbial methane oxidation: Improved determination. *Waste Manag.* **26**:
183 389–398. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2005.11.006
- 184 Mariotti, A., J. C. Germon, P. Hubert, P. Kaiser, R. Letolle, A. Tardieux, and P. Tardieux. 1981.
185 Experimental determination of nitrogen kinetic isotope fractionation: Some principles; illustration
186 for the denitrification and nitrification processes. *Plant Soil* **62**: 413–430.
187 doi:10.1007/BF02374138
- 188 Page, M. J. and others. 2021. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic
189 reviews. *BMJ* n71. doi:10.1136/bmj.n71
- 190 Stanley, E. H., L. C. Loken, N. J. Casson, S. K. Oliver, R. A. Sponseller, M. B. Wallin, L. Zhang, and G.
191 Rocher-Ros. 2023. GRiMeDB: the Global River Methane Database of concentrations and fluxes.
192 *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **15**: 2879–2926. doi:10.5194/essd-15-2879-2023
- 193 Wilkinson, J., C. Bors, F. Burgis, A. Lorke, and P. Bodmer. 2018. Measuring CO₂ and CH₄ with a
194 portable gas analyzer: Closed-loop operation, optimization and assessment V. Gupta [ed.]. *PLOS*
195 *ONE* **13**: e0193973. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0193973